

The Smart City Concept and the Expansion of Public Spaces

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Abstract

This article investigates the connection between urban public spaces and emerging technologies in smart cities, addressing a significant gap in comparative research between the Global South and North. To bridge this gap, this study examines São Paulo, a Latin American metropolis in Brazil, and Berlin, a European city in Germany, highlighting their initiatives to develop interactive urban environments despite differing urban policies and socioeconomic conditions. The primary research question explores whether smart cities can be built on ethical, aesthetic, digital communication structures and artificial intelligence resources, focusing on social inclusion and integration for urban environmental sustainability. Additionally, the study examines how digital and physical environments can be integrated to create more human-centered urban spaces. Two core dimensions are explored: urban spatial models and transformative digital structures that shape alternative realities and interactive communities. The methodology employs qualitative and quantitative approaches, including empirical studies conducted in the two cities. Qualitative methods like observation reveal social phenomena in public spaces, while quantitative tools assess technology integration and public engagement. The findings emphasize the necessity of aligning technological innovations with ethical values and community needs, promoting human-centered urbanism focused on accessibility, cultural diversity, and sustainability despite varying developments in education and social well-being.

Keywords: smart cities, human-centered design, public interest, social inclusion, sustainability